

8

TH INTERNATIONAL

SLAG VALORISATION SYMPOSIUM

TACKLING FUTURE CRITICAL CHALLENGES

18-20 April 2023

Mechelen, Belgium

PROCEEDINGS

KU LEUVEN

MATERIALS ENGINEERING

KU LEUVEN

SIM2

KU Leuven Institute for Sustainable Metals and Minerals

FUMING PROCESS OF ZINC-RICH SLAGS BY HYDROGEN INJECTION

Gunnar HOVESTADT, Bernd FRIEDRICH

Institute of Process Metallurgy and Metal Recycling (IME) RWTH Aachen, 52066, Germany

ghovestadt@ime-aachen.de, bfriedrich@ime-aachen.de

Introduction

The fuming of Zinc and Lead from lead smelting slags is done since 1927¹. The process is a reductive evaporation of zinc and lead, which is normally done with carbon carriers and air addition^{2,3}. For a higher vapour pressure and faster evaporation zinc oxide has to be reduced to a metallic state at temperatures around 1200 to 1400°C¹. After reduction, it will evaporate immediately caused by a vapour pressure of more than 10 bar⁴. The evaporated zinc bubble will leave the melt by itself or is collected by the introduced air¹. The efficiency of zinc fuming is in industrial cases up to 90%², but can reach up to 96% in experiments⁵.

The reduction of greenhouse gases is a new push for technology developments. The replacement of carbon by hydrogen in the metallurgical sector is one of the green options for the future. For the fuming process, it is thermochemically possible to reduce zinc oxide with hydrogen at temperatures above 1200°C⁶. Figure 1 shows the FactSage™ 8.2⁶ calculated Gibbs free energy over temperature for pure substances. It can be seen, that also lead could be reduced. Another advantage of the injection with gaseous reduction agents is the large and flexible reaction surface of the bubbles which has no equilibrium reaction with solids like carbon particles in air ($C \leftrightarrow CO$)⁵. In comparison to natural gas hydrogen has not to be cracked into C and H₂ before the reaction, leading to faster kinetics and higher efficiencies⁷. The higher molar volume of

Figure 1: Diagram of free Gibbs reaction energies of different hydrogen reduction reactions with pure substances calculated with FactSage's 8.2 Pure Substances database¹

hydrogen instead of other reduction agents leads to a high gas volume, which could also improve the process.

Experimental equipment

For the experimental procedure, a resistant heated furnace was used. It has a power input with a maximum of 31 kW and a limitation in temperature at 1400°C. Inside the furnace, a refractory-lined grey-graphite crucible was used. The lining was made with Didurit (Al₂O₃-Cr₂O₃, RHI AG, Austria). A lid was made of the same refractory material to isolate the melt from the atmosphere and guarantee constant temperatures. The injection lance is made of strong sintered corundum. On top, a refractory tube was used to minimise thermal losses from the furnace. The gas mixing station was made of mass flow controllers (Bürkert GmbH, Germany). The Gases used have a purity of 99.999 vol.% nitrogen and 99.9 vol.% hydrogen.

Figure 2: Schematic side view of the used setup

Two types of slag were used in the experiments, which are shown in Table 1. Reduced fayalitic copper slag from the primary process is used with 1.2 wt% zinc, 0.3 wt% lead and copper content of 0.9 wt%. The secondary, fayalitic slag has a high zinc content of 4.1 wt%, a low amount of copper 0.7 wt% and 0.2 wt% lead.

Table 1: Features of the predefined styles to be used in your paper

wt%	Fe	Si	Ca	Al	Cu	Zn	Pb	Ni	Sn	rest
Primary	38.8	15.3	1.7	2.4	0.9	1.2	0.3	< 0.1	< 0.1	39.4
Secondary	30.9	10.3	2.5	2.9	0.7	3.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	49.2

In Table 2 the overview of planned experiments is shown. The temperature for all experiments is kept constant at 1300°C. There are 3 different hydrogen concentrations tested for each, primary and secondary, slag. The flow rate is also kept constant to ensure comparable mixing behaviour in the slag phase. Every pair of parameters was done twice to consolidate the results. The amount of slag was chosen to be 1.5 kg, due to the filling level of the crucible.

Table 2: Overview of experimental trials with parameters

Trial number	Temperature [°C]	Slag type	Hydrogen [vol.%]	Flow rate [l/min]
1 / 2	1300	Primary	15	2.0
3 / 4			45	
5 / 6			75	
7 / 8		Secondary	50	
9 / 10			75	
11 / 12			100	

Results

In the experiment, three products could be obtained. Besides the slag phase, a copper-rich metal phase could be found and a generation of flue dust was seen. Recovery of the dust could not be carried out in the small-scale experiments. Deposition of dust on the lance and above the lid show white and yellow/orange colours. This could conclude to the presence of zinc and lead oxides. Also, the visual generation of dust is decreasing within the trials with primary slags.

Figure 3: Results of reduction of secondary slag (left) and primary slag (right) with different hydrogen concentrations at 1300°C with a constant flow rate of 2 l/min

In Figure 3 the concentrations of zinc (grey) and lead (black) are shown for 3 concentrations of each slag. For primary slag on the left side, the starting point of zinc concentration is 1.1 wt% decreasing down to 0.01 wt% with 15 and 75 vol.%. By using a higher hydrogen concentration, the fuming time could be decreased by the factor of the

concentration. 45 vol.% hydrogen in the injection gas decreases the content of zinc to 0.2 wt%, however, the reduction stopped after 2/3 of the injection time. The curves of zinc show an exponential shape for high hydrogen concentrations while the small hydrogen concentration could also be linear fitted. The influence of diffusion seems to get higher with low zinc levels and high hydrogen concentrations, while small concentrations stay reaction controlled. In the case of lead, the concentration could be lowered to 0.04 wt% with all tested hydrogen concentrations. Here the factor of time could also be decreased by the factor of concentration. Thus, the increase of hydrogen decreases the time by its factor. It could be said, that the efficiency of hydrogen reaction seems to be the same for all concentrations, due to same final zinc and lead concentrations by a constant hydrogen amount injected.

For secondary slags with a higher zinc content of around 3 wt% a strong decrease could be obtained. There was no trend found for the hydrogen concentration, due to the fact that 50% hydrogen has a higher slope than 75%. Only 100% hydrogen shows the best results. With the addition of 90 l hydrogen a final content of 0.7 to 1.3 wt% zinc could be reached. If more hydrogen would be injected the content is supposed to decrease further, as seen with primary slag. The concentration of lead is decreased to values of 0.02 wt% at the end of the injection time. In contrast to zinc, the slopes of the lead decreases are proportional to the hydrogen concentration. Due to this fact it seems like there is an analytical mistake or different bubbling behaviour at the end of the lance resulting in the different order for zinc removal.

Discussion

The experimental data shows, that the fuming of zinc and lead with hydrogen works in a sufficient way. The efficiency of hydrogen seems to be constant over a high range of reduction gas concentration, due to similar final contents. Therefore, a high concentration could decrease the processing time significantly. The lowest contents of lead and zinc achieved are 0.04 and 0.2 wt% for primary and 0.02 and 0.49 wt% for secondary slag. Higher zinc concentrations seem to have a linear trend, while concentrations below 1 wt% have an exponential shape. Within the fuming process, the diffusion of zinc oxide in the slag phase seems to get higher importance.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank their technical staff for supporting this publication. This investigation is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 958307.

References

1. R. G. Reddy, V. Prabhu, D. Mantha, "Zinc Fuming from Lead Blast Furnace Slag," *High Temperature Materials and Processes*, **21**, No. 6, 2002, pp. 377–386.
2. Z. Cheng, A. Khaliq, B. Blanpain, B., M. Guo, "Zn Fuming Kinetics in a Bubble-Stirred Molten Slag Bath," *Metall Mater Trans B*, **53**, No. 2, 2022, pp. 1308–1319.
3. S. Jahanshahi, S. Wright, "Kinetics of Reduction of CaO-FeO x -MgO-PbO-SiO₂ Slags by CO-CO₂ Gas Mixtures," *Metall Mater Trans B*, **48**, No. 4, 2017, pp. 2057–2066.
4. M. Schmid, "Vapor pressure calculator," 2013-2019, https://www.iap.tuwien.ac.at/www/surface/vapor_pressure.
5. G. Richards, J. K. Brimacombe, "Kinetics of the zinc slag-Fuming process: Part III. model predictions and analysis of process kinetics," *Metall Mater Trans B*, **16**, No. 3, 1985, pp. 541–549.
6. Bale, C. e. a., "FactSage Thermochemical Software and Databases," V. 2016, *Calphad* **54**, 2010 - 2016, pp. 35–53.
7. T. Edens, J. Steindor, "Using Hydrogen as a Reductant in Fire Refining at Aurubis Hamburg's "Downtown" Smelter," Proceedings of the 61st Conference of Metallurgists, COM 2022, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2023, pp. 211–228.